

Survey on AI/ML Pipeline Development Practices (FR/EN)

The present survey is part of the "Intent-Driven Low-Code Development" research project, supported by

The goal of this project is to explore and understand the **practices, challenges, and needs** of researchers across various scientific fields in **designing and using artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) pipelines**. An AI/ML pipeline is a structured sequence of steps used to prepare data, build, train, evaluate, and deploy AI/ML models that support research or decision-making.

This survey aims to **gather information on how researchers from different domains develop and use AI/ML pipelines in their work**.

The responses will help investigate how low-code approaches can improve the accessibility and quality of these pipelines, particularly for researchers with varying levels of expertise in programming and AI/ML

requer

Consent

Confidentiality of Collected Information: Participation in this survey is entirely anonymous: no personal data is collected.

The survey takes between 10 and 20 minutes to complete. Participation is unpaid, and offers no direct benefit, but it will help guide the design of an open-access low-code platform for researchers using AI in their projects.

Voluntary Participation and Right to Withdraw: Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may stop at any time without consequence; any partially completed responses will not be used. However, due to the anonymity of the data, responses cannot be withdrawn after their submission. By agreeing to participate in this study, you do not waive any of your rights, nor do you release the researchers or the institution from their legal and professional responsibilities.

Use of Data and Dissemination of Results: The collected data will be used to inform the design of a low-code platform aimed at facilitating the integration of AI into research work. The data will also be analyzed for scientific publications. No other use will be made of the data.

Contact Persons / Principal Investigators:

For any concerns regarding your rights or the responsibilities of the researchers related to your participation in this project, you may contact the Research Ethics Committee for Science and Health (CERSES)

Any complaint related to your participation in this research may be directed to the

1. Please select one of the following responses: *

- I consent to participate
- I do not consent to participate

General Information

First, we would like to collect demographic and professional data to understand the diversity of profiles and skills among researchers using artificial intelligence and machine learning (IA/ML) in their research.

2. What is your primary research area? Please select the closest option:

- Natural sciences
- Engineering and technology
- Medical, health or life sciences
- Agricultural or veterinary sciences
- Social sciences
- Humanities and the arts

Domain: Natural Sciences

3. What is your discipline in Natural Sciences?

- Mathematics or statistics
- Computer or information sciences
- Physical sciences
- Chemical sciences
- Earth or related environmental sciences
- Biological sciences
- Other

Domain: Engineering and Technology

4. What is your discipline in Engineering and Technology?

- Civil engineering, maritime engineering, transport engineering, or mining engineering
- Industrial, systems or processes engineering
- Electrical engineering, computer engineering, or information engineering
- Mechanical engineering
- Chemical engineering
- Materials engineering or resources engineering
- Medical or biomedical engineering
- Environmental engineering or related engineering
- Environmental biotechnology
- Industrial biotechnology
- Nano-technology
- Other

Domain: Medical, Health and Life Sciences

5. What is your discipline in Medical, Health and life Sciences?

- Basic medicine or life sciences
- Clinical medicine
- Health sciences
- Medical biotechnology
- Other

Domain: Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences

6. What is your discipline in Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences?

- Agriculture, forestry, or fisheries
- Animal or dairy sciences
- Veterinary sciences
- Agricultural biotechnology or food sciences
- Other

Domain: Social Sciences

7. What is your discipline in Social Sciences?

- Psychology or cognitive sciences
- Economics or business administration
- Education
- Sociology or related studies
- Law and legal practice
- Political science or policy administration
- Social or economic geography
- Media or communications
- Other

Domain: Humanities and the Arts

8. What is your discipline in Humanities and the Arts?

- History, archaeology or related studies
- Languages or literature
- Philosophy
- Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music), architecture and design
- Other

General Information (Continued)

First, we would like to collect demographic and professional data to understand the diversity of profiles and skills among researchers using artificial intelligence and machine learning (IA/ML) in their research.

9. What is your current academic or professional status?

- Undergraduate Student
- Graduate Student
- Postdoc Researcher / Researcher
- Professor
- Other

10. How would you describe your programming or coding skill level?

- No experience: I have never written code
- Beginner: I have basic familiarity with coding but have limited hands-on experience
- Intermediate: I can write and modify code for specific tasks, but may need guidance
- Advanced: I can develop, debug, and optimize complex programs independently
- Expert: I have extensive experience in coding, software development, and advanced systems programming

11. What is your primary source of training in programming or coding?

- No formal training, self-taught
- Online courses or tutorials
- Practical training through technical schools or certificate programs
- University training (1–2 courses)
- University training (more than 2 courses)
- Other

12. How would you describe your experience level in AI/ML?

- No experience: I have never worked with AI/ML
- Beginner: I have a basic understanding but limited hands-on experience
- Intermediate: I have implemented AI/ML models and worked with common AI/ML tools
- Advanced: I have significant experience in developing and optimizing AI/ML models.
- Expert: I have deep expertise in AI/ML, including research, development, or deployment of complex AI systems
- Other

13. What is your primary source of training in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning ?

- No formal training, self-taught
- Online course or tutorials
- Practical training through technical schools or certificate programs
- University training (1–2 courses)
- University training (more than 2 courses)
- Other

14. How would you describe your programming proficiency when it comes to implementing AI/ML pipelines?

In what follows, we called an *AI/ML pipeline* a step-by-step process used to prepare data, apply artificial intelligence or machine learning methods, and produce results that support research or decision-making.

- Low: I rely on existing scripts or others to do most of the coding
- Moderate: I can write and modify code, but am not an expert
- High: I am very comfortable coding anything needed for my AI pipelines
- Expert: I have expert-level coding skills specifically for AI/ML development
- Other

The Research Problems

Now, we would like to understand the type of research problems you are addressing with AI/ML pipelines.

15. What types of AI/ML tasks are you using to address your research problems? (Select all that apply)

- Clustering: Identifying patterns and grouping data points based on similarity
- Natural Language Processing: Analyzing and understanding human language data
- Anomaly Detection: Identifying rare or unusual events in data
- Regression: Predicting continuous numerical outcomes from input features
- Reinforcement Learning: Training models based on rewards and feedback from actions
- Classification: Predicting discrete (labels)
- Generation: Creating new data (e.g., text, images, audio) using learned patterns
- Simulation or modeling: Creating virtual models to replicate real-world processes or systems
- Computer Vision: Interpreting and processing image or video data
- Optimization: Finding the best solutions in complex systems
- Human-AI Interaction: Designing and studying systems where humans and AI collaborate
- Time series of forecasting: Predicting future values based on time-ordered data
- Other

16. What types of data do you primarily use in your research? (Select all that apply)

- Tabular Data: Structured rows and columns (e.g., spreadsheets, databases)
- Textual Data: Unstructured or structured text (e.g., documents, social media, chat logs, transcripts)
- Image Data (e.g., Photos, medical scans, satellite images)
- Audio Data (e.g., recorded conversations, music, voice commands)
- Video Data (e.g., surveillance footage, motion capture, video streams)
- Time-Series Data (e.g., financial data, sensor data)
- Graph Data (e.g., social networks, knowledge graphs)
- Genomic or biological data
- Simulation-generated data
- Synthetic Data: AI-generated or augmented datasets
- Other

17. What is the estimated size of your typical datasets (in terms of items)?

- Dozens (10–99 data points)
- Hundreds (100–999 data points)
- Thousands (1,000–9,999 data points)
- Tens of Thousands (10,000–99,999 data points)
- Hundreds of Thousands (100,000–999,999 data points)
- Millions or More (1,000,000+ data points)
- Other

18. Do your AI pipelines need to comply with any ethical, regulatory, or data governance frameworks?

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure

AI/ML Pipeline Development Practices

In this part, we are trying to understand how you usually develop AI/ML pipelines in your research.

19. How do you typically develop an AI/ML pipeline in your research? (Select all that apply)

- Work with collaborators or consultants who build the pipeline
- Write code from scratch (e.g., in Python, R, Matlab)
- Use pre-trained models or APIs (e.g., OpenAI, Hugging Face, Google AutoML)
- Use software libraries or frameworks (e.g., scikit-learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch)
- Use low-code or no-code tools (e.g., KNIME, Orange, AutoML platforms)
- Use existing scripts or notebooks and adapt them
- Other

20. Do you work with AI/ML specialists to develop these pipelines?

- I develop AI pipelines entirely on my own
- I collaborate occasionally with AI/ML specialists
- I work closely and regularly with AI/ML specialists
- Other

21. If you collaborate, which tasks are typically handled by AI/ML specialists? (Select all that apply)

- Model evaluation and validation
- Model selection and training
- Feature engineering
- Problem framing / defining the ML task
- Model deployment and integration
- Data cleaning and preprocessing
- Code optimization and reproducibility
- Other

22. If you collaborate, what stages of the AI pipeline do you typically work on? (Select all that apply)

- Model Evaluation (Assessing the performance of trained model)
- Model Selection (Choosing the most appropriate algorithm or model architecture)
- Data Preprocessing (Cleaning, transforming, and organizing raw data into a usable format)
- Data Collection (Gathering raw data from various sources such as databases, APIs, experiments, or sensors)
- Feature Engineering (Selecting or Creating Relevant Input Variables)
- Monitoring and Maintenance (Tracking the model's performance over time)
- Other

23. Any additional comment about your AI/ML pipeline development practices?

Tools and Platforms

This section identifies the tools, frameworks, and platforms commonly used for AI/ML development and explores existing limitations, as well as overall satisfaction, with current AI development tools.

24. Which tools, frameworks, or platforms do you commonly use for AI/ML pipeline development? (Select all that apply)

- Jupyter or other interactive notebooks (e.g., JupyterLab, Google Colab)
- Machine learning libraries/frameworks (e.g., scikit-learn, TensorFlow, PyTorch, Keras)
- Cloud computing platforms or services (e.g., AWS SageMaker, Azure ML Studio, Google AI Platform)
- Programming language environments (e.g., Python scripts, R Studio, MATLAB)
- Automated machine learning platforms (e.g., Google AutoML, [H2O.ai](#), KNIME, Microsoft Power Platform, Appian, Nextflow, Orange, Node-RED)
- Other

25. What are the most important factors in selecting an AI development tool or platform for your work?

Please select at most 3 options.

- Cost / licensing
- Flexibility / customizability
- Community support / documentation
- Support for low-code / no-code development
- Visualization capabilities
- Performance / speed
- Integration with other tools or systems
- Ease of use
- Security and data privacy
- Other

26. What are the biggest limitations of your current tools?

- Limited model customization
- Limited documentation or support
- Security or privacy concerns
- Cost or licensing constraints
- Incompatibility with my data formats
- Too complex or difficult to use
- Poor performance with large datasets
- Lack of collaborative features
- Limited visualization or interpretability features
- Lack of integration with other tools
- Other

27. Overall, how satisfied are you with your current primary tools/platforms for AI pipeline development?

- Very satisfied: The tools fully meet my needs and work efficiently
- Satisfied: The tools are generally effective, but have some limitations
- Neutral: The tools are neither particularly helpful nor problematic
- Dissatisfied: The tools have significant issues that limit my work
- Very dissatisfied: The tools are inadequate and create major obstacles

28. Do you have any additional comments about your experience with AI/ML tools?

Challenges in AI/ML Pipeline Development

Almost done! Please tell us more about the challenges you face when using AI/ML in your research.

29. What are the biggest challenges you face when working with AI in your research? (Please select at most 3 options)

Please select at most 3 options.

- Connecting AI to other tools or systems: Integrating AI into existing research workflows or applications
- Choosing the right data features: Selecting the most relevant information for the AI to learn from
- Making AI models ready for real-world use: Preparing and deploying AI for practical applications
- Translating the research problem into an AI task: Challenges in specifying the AI system's purpose and determining how to structure it to meet research goals.
- Adjusting AI settings for better performance: Experimenting with different configurations to improve accuracy
- Selecting the right AI method or model: Deciding which approach works best for your problem
- Limited programming knowledge: Challenges in coding or implementing AI models without external help
- Fixing errors or unexpected results: Debugging and troubleshooting AI performance issues
- Lack of specialized AI tools: Few or no AI tools designed for my specific research area
- Finding or preparing good-quality data: Collecting, cleaning, and organizing data for AI models
- Other

30. Additional comments on the challenges you face when using AI in your research?

Building AI Pipelines with Low-Code Platforms

Low-code and *no-code* platforms allow users to build software applications with little or no programming, using visual interfaces and preconfigured components. They are designed to make development more accessible, even for those without deep programming expertise.

In this final section, we'd like to learn more about your current (or potential future) use of such platforms in your research.

31. Do you use no-code or low-code platforms for developing AI models or pipelines (tools that allow AI development with minimal coding)?

- Yes, regularly: I often use no-code/low-code AI tools (e.g., Azure ML Studio, Google AutoML, KNIME)
- Occasionally, for specific tasks
- I have tried them but don't use them anymore
- I know about them but have never used them
- I am not familiar with these platforms
- Other

32. Why don't you use the low-code platform regularly?

- Limited flexibility or customizability
- Not powerful enough for my needs
- Lack of support for my type of data or models
- Integration issues with other tools or workflows
- Concerns about transparency or interpretability
- Lack of awareness or training
- I prefer full control through coding
- Other

33. What type of interface would you prefer for AI/ML pipeline development? (Select all that apply)

- Notebook environment (e.g., Jupyter, Google Colab): I like using interactive notebooks that let me combine code, visualizations, and narrative text in one environment.
- Command-line interface (CLI): I prefer working in terminal-based environments where I can run scripts and commands directly.
- Graphical interface with drag-and-drop modules: I prefer visual tools that let me build pipelines by connecting components through a graphical interface, without needing to write code.
- Code editor (e.g., Python, R, Matlab): I prefer writing code manually to have full control over the pipeline's logic and structure.
- Hybrid interface (code + visual elements): I prefer platforms that offer both coding and visual tools, allowing me to customize parts of the pipeline while benefiting from a user-friendly interface.
- Other

34. How should a low-code AI tool allow you to incorporate your domain expertise into the AI pipeline?

- Allow me to define or modify parts of the pipeline manually
- Suggest pipeline components based on my problem or data
- Adapt to my level of programming or AI knowledge
- Let me validate or override system-generated suggestions
- Include options tailored to my research domain
- Other

35. Are there any missing tools or features you would like to have to make AI pipeline development easier?

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